

THE ADVANTAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF THE FINANCIAL MARKET IN UZBEKISTAN

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This thesis focuses the ability of developing country governments to borrow from international credit markets over the different stages of the international credit market cycle. The thesis also analyzes the practice of Uzbekistan, as a developing country, sovereign borrowing. In addition, the impact of these government Eurobonds on the country's economy has been studied on the basis of statistical analysis.

Keywords: Eurobond, Global bond, Parallel bond, Foreign bond, sovereign borrowing, coupon rate, maturity, government sovereign Eurobonds, international capital market, benchmark.

International bonds, in particular Eurobonds as one of the levers of financing, are, as a rule, a stock market instrument in the long term, providing less risk for its holder. If it is compared this instrument, with such a security as shares, then it can be safely said that, due to the high guarantees of servicing coupon payments, the circulation of bonds requires a transparent and rating assessment of the financial condition of the issuer.

The ability of a sovereign government to borrow on international credit markets depends on its perceived ability to repay and on the incentives it will have to do it. International bonds are considered one of the instruments of the international credit market. In turn, the international credit market is part of the international financial market. The main difference between the international credit market and the national or state one is that transactions with securities occur with resident investors and non-resident issuers who conduct their activities on the basis of international law. The similarity of the international stock market with the state one is that there is also a transfer of capital between several countries. Consequently, securities circulating in the territory of only one country, going beyond its borders, are now referred to as euro securities. It should be taken into account that the prefix "euro" does not mean that this financial instrument belongs only to European countries, although it used to be so before. Now this is a sign that this security may have property rights of absolutely different entities from different parts of the world.

J. Eaton and M. Gersovitz in their scientific article noted that "Access to international capital markets is likely to be the result of demand and supply factors: disentangling these two would require an exogenous shock in the demand or in the supply schedule. Focusing exclusively on emerging markets and developing economies (many of which are low-income developing countries) should help minimize the cases of voluntarily absence from the market (lack of demand), given that these countries generally need large amounts of external funds to finance domestic investment. Countries, however, could still self-select out of international credit markets, especially in the case of sovereigns with sufficient access to grants and concessional loans. In addition, countries could base their demand for international bonds on expected borrowing costs. While it is difficult to fully control for these costs, especially for first-time issuers for whom there are no secondary market bond spreads, the information on expected borrowing costs is indirectly taken into account by inclusion of a comprehensive set of domestic and global controls in the selection equation. However, in the absence of an

identification strategy, the empirical exercise focuses on factors associated with sovereign bond issuance without implying causality.”

For any borrowing country, entering the international financial market is associated with a number of goals that they pursue. These goals must be justified, since the country will face a number of innovations during the issue, which can seriously affect the image of the country. For example, for many countries it becomes impossible to obtain a good credit rating, which automatically affects the liquidity of Euro papers. Or, for many countries, the factor of openness of the economy calls into question the issuance of Eurobonds.

Analyzing the activities of the Republican Stock Exchange "Tashkent", we can see how the volume of trading increased sharply, but given the subsequent depreciation of the Uzbek currency and GDP growth rates, such indicators are not so significant. Many specialists in the financial sector have developed special forms of mechanisms for issuing Eurobonds, which have become a guideline, or a kind of "model" for new participants in the international stock market.

“By the Decree of the President of December 26, 2018 “On the forecast of the main macroeconomic indicators and parameters of the State budget of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019” The Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan was instructed "during 2019 to issue and place sovereign bonds of the Republic of Uzbekistan at a fixed coupon rate for an amount not less than 500 million US dollars with a maturity of 5 or more years.

On February 14, 2019, Uzbekistan placed the debut two tranches of Eurobonds with a total volume of \$1 billion, as published by the London Stock Exchange. The bonds were placed in a double tranche of \$500 million with maturities in 2024 and 2029.

According to the resolution, in order to effectively use the funds received from the placement of Eurobonds of the Republic of Uzbekistan, including for financing investment projects that have strategies important for the further improvement of the welfare of the country and the population, proposals were submitted by the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Central Bank. The received 459.6 million US dollars on 5-year sovereign Eurobonds were placed in commercial banks with a term of 5 years, that is, until February 10 2024. In this case, a 5-year term deposit in foreign currency is placed at a minimum annual rate of 5.25% and is interest income. It should also be noted that the rate of 5.25% is set based on the margin of 4.75% plus 0.5%, at which sovereign Eurobonds are placed. In addition, interest on these deposits is paid by commercial banks every six months, that is, until February 10, 2024, February 10 and August 10 of each year.

In turn, funds from 10-year sovereign eurobonds of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the amount of 429.6 million US dollars were placed on the basis of an auction between joint-stock companies merchant banks until February 10, 2029, i.e. for this period of time, a 10-year deposit in foreign currency is provided with a minimum annual rate of 5.875% and interest income is accrued. It should also be noted that the rate of 5.875% is set on the basis of a margin of 5.325% plus 0.5%, placed on 10-year sovereign Eurobonds.

Nine months after the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the country's national banks also begin issuing Eurobonds for foreign investors. The first in this arena was the domestic bank Uzpromstroybank. Being one of the largest banks of the republic and at the same time a strategic one, Uzpromstroybank placed its first corporate Eurobonds for a period

of 5 years on the London Stock Exchange. Their coupon yield was determined after the auction as 5.75% per annum for a total of \$300 million.

Many specialists were interested in buying Uzpromstroybank's corporate Eurobonds due to their strategic goals, which explains the increase in investor applications by \$1.2 billion.

Thus, Uzpromstroybank has become a benchmark for other Uzbek corporate structures interested in attracting foreign capital through the international stock market, on the one hand, and on the other hand, opened access for foreign investors to the domestic securities market.

The funds received from the issue of Eurobonds will be used to increase the economic and competitive power of this commercial bank. However, a concrete and transparent project plan has not been demonstrated to outsiders.

Another bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan that has successfully become a participant in the international financial market is the National Bank for Foreign Economic Affairs of Uzbekistan.

The international rating agency Fitch Ratings has assigned this bank a BB- credit rating, meaning "expected long-term rating". Their debut issue was set at \$300 million. The circulation period of the National Bank's Eurobonds was 5 years. Due to the high demand of investors and the fact that it exceeds the volume of the issue twice, the final coupon value amounting to 4.85% per year decreased by 0.30% of the initial interest rate during trading.

Such a successful placement of Eurobonds by the bank indicates a positive assessment by international investors of the reforms being carried out in the country.

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According to the analytical data of the National Bank, the proceeds from the issue of corporate Eurobonds are planned to be used to finance the bank's foreign loan portfolio.

The issued Eurobonds are very popular among foreign investors thanks to which the coupon rate can be reduced by several points. Each of the issues is accompanied by a high volume of applications, which indicates that investors are interested in buying securities in a country that until recently had a closed economy. All coupon rates have approximately the same value, which indicates that national issuers are still cautious about setting coupon rates.

The development of the financial market led to a noticeable increase in its share in the national economy. Now the participants of the financial market, government regulators and the scientific community are faced with the question of further ways to develop this sector of the economy and increase its efficiency.

Upon reaching the goals of becoming a professional participant in the international stock market, the issuing country will be able to use the variety of instruments of the international stock market, increase the investment attractiveness of the country by publishing its micro and macroeconomic indicators. In addition, the issuing country can strengthen the level of confidence on the part of domestic and foreign investors. Such a result will lead to full transparency of the economy for external users, which will positively affect the timely replenishment of the state budget through state taxes. In addition, the status of a professional participant in the global stock market will affect the formation of inexpensive education

capital for some organizations in need of funding. Attraction of external financing will solve the problems of refinancing and debt restructuring.

As shown by the analysis of debt issues of Eurobonds by national issuers, the following can be attributed to the advantages of participating in the global borrowing market:

1. The national stock market of the Republic of Uzbekistan today is not sufficiently capital-intensive, and, accordingly, does not solve the problem of cheap financing. Well, entering the world loan capital market, we improve our macroeconomic indicators and, as a result, become investment attractive for large potential investors.
2. The issuance of Eurobonds helps to avoid the marginal costs of transactions associated with obligations, and as a result, financing the state budget is the cheapest in relation to other forms of issuing financial market instruments.
3. The high demand for debut tranches of Eurobonds from foreign investors is explained by the fact that our country has been pursuing a policy of protectionism for a long time, and entering the world stock market has become the beginning of cooperation with many countries. Also positive for the investment policy is the fact that our country has received a credit rating from major international rating agencies, which have previously studied and analyzed the financial condition of the issuer, and then on an ongoing basis will monitor the activities in relation to their requirements.

References:

1. Andrea F. Presbitero, Dhaneshwar Ghura, Olumuyiwa S. Adedeji, and Lamin Njie. "International Sovereign Bonds by Emerging Markets and Developing Economies: Drivers of Issuance and Spreads" WP/15/275, IMF.
2. Eaton, J., and Gersovitz, M., (1980). "LDC participation in international financial markets: Debt and reserves", *Journal of Development Economics*, 7(1): 3-21.
3. Gelos, G.R., Sahay, R., and Sandleris, G., (2011). "Sovereign borrowing by developing countries: What determines market access?" *Journal of International Economics*, 83: 243-254.
4. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan: № PD-4258 dated April 2, 2019 "On the effective use of funds from the placement of the first sovereign international bonds of the Republic of Uzbekistan".